

Human trafficking is a problem of the time

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Sarvinoz Ulug`bekova,

2nd year of student,

Namangan State University.

Annotation: *This article discusses the efforts made to prevent and combat human trafficking, the results of decisions and decrees, and the ideas put forward in the fight against human trafficking among young people.*

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Nowadays human trafficking is one of the evils that is becoming a problem of the century, allowing the whole world to be endangered and living a life of constant fear and anxiety. We usually refer to a transaction between a buyer and a seller as a trade. However, the fact that the concept of 'human trafficking' is not just a product but a sale of a living soul calls us all to be equally vigilant. This 'trade' that is shaking the world is not only observed in our state.

Human trafficking is a business of stealing freedom for profit. In some cases, human traffickers deceive, defraud, or physically coerce victims. In other cases, victims are manipulated to lie, attack, threaten, or work in inhumane, illegal, or otherwise unacceptable conditions. It is a multi-billion dollar criminal industry that deprives 24.9 million people of their liberty worldwide. Scroll down for more information on what human trafficking is. We hope this information is helpful to you. Keep in mind that the National Helpline staff is focused on helping victims and survivors and cannot answer more general questions about human trafficking for their work or research or other purposes.

Large-scale scientific and practical reforms to combat human trafficking are being carried out in small countries and large countries. But no matter how hard you try, it will not be easy for any country to eradicate this scourge from the world.

It should be noted that great work is being done in our country to prevent and combat human trafficking.

In particular, on 12 December 2003, Uzbekistan acceded to the 1950 Convention on the Suppression of Human trafficking and the Prostitution of Others by the UN General Assembly, and on 17 April 2008 the Law on Combating human trafficking was adopted. According to this law, human trafficking is the use of force, threats or use of force or other forms of coercion, theft, fraud, deception, abuse of power or risk of the situation, or by obtaining the consent of another person in exchange for payment or means hiring, transporting, handing over, hiding or accepting people for the purpose of using them by taking.

At the same time, in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 30, 2019 "On additional measures to further improve the system of combating human trafficking and forced labor" reorganized.

In addition, our country doesn't stop fighting against human trafficking. As a result, in our country there are people committing this heinous crime today. Therefore, on August 17, 2020, our country adopted a new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On combating human trafficking" № ZRU-633.

The law sets out the following key areas in the fight against human trafficking, including:

- implementation of legal, political, socio-economic, medical, preventive measures, information measures aimed at preventing human trafficking, including raising the legal awareness and legal culture of the population;
- to take measures to combat human trafficking, including the elimination of the causes and conditions that facilitate human trafficking;
- timely detection and suppression of human trafficking, elimination of its consequences, as well as ensuring the principle of inevitability of liability of traffickers;
- state support, including social protection, for victims of human trafficking and those suspected of being victims of trafficking;
- development and promotion of research, conferences, seminars, trainings and roundtables in the field of combating human trafficking, as well as training, retraining and advanced training of government officials in this field ;
- international cooperation in the fight against human trafficking.

Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan may work abroad only on the basis of intergovernmental, interdepartmental agreements concluded by the Republic of Uzbekistan with foreign countries. The illegal income from this crime is estimated at 7 billion US dollars. Worldwide, between 600,000 and 800,000 women and children are trafficked each year. It is particularly

sad that 80 percent of victims of trafficking are women or young children. In order to prevent such scandals as human trafficking and drug trafficking, various scientific and practical conferences and meetings are held in our country.

Holding such meetings will greatly increase the spiritual potential of young people, raise their legal culture and prevent future generations from being surrounded by physical and spiritual threats.

A number of measures have been taken by the regional commission over the past period. In particular, warning devices are being installed in places that can be seen in the district centers of our city. Talks and meetings are being held with those who want to work abroad. However, many men and women abroad are now suffering from this scourge. Many of them still do not understand their rights, are lost and are looking for ways to return to their homeland. The simplicity and confidence of our citizens in the recruitment of slaves, the desire to solve financial problems quickly, the desire to find an easy job, the lack of legal knowledge, the narrow-mindedness of the victims of crime, the shallowness of the world remain.

Through this article, I would like to say that all citizens of our republic and our compatriots working abroad as labor migrants should not be deceived and fall into the trap of human traffickers, not to believe in false promises such as easy and effortless enrichment. I urge you to actively monitor the problem-solving processes and, most importantly, to be vigilant.

The proclamation of July 30 as World Anti-Trafficking Day by the United Nations in 2013 encouraged humanity to fight this crime.

Every year, the Tashkent Medical Academy prepares a wide audience to fight against human trafficking and explain its tragic consequences, especially among young people, to prevent them from becoming victims of this heinous crime, youth events are being organized.

As noted in the Address of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, "Protecting the constitutional order, sovereignty and territorial integrity of our country from various threats, further strengthening peace and stability is the key to all our achievements".

Today, a number of measures are being taken to prevent and combat human trafficking, which is one of the most pressing issues in our country. At the same time, given that human trafficking is a transnational crime, our country has acceded to the UN General Assembly Convention on Combating human trafficking and Prostitution, adopted by the UN General Assembly on December 12, 2003. The Convention on the Prevention, Combating and Punishment of Trafficking in Persons, in particular Women

and Children, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 15 November 2000, an additional protocol was also ratified.

In short, the fight against any form of human trafficking can only be effective if it is based on a serious approach and cooperation at the international and regional levels.

Indeed, human trafficking, the unlawful and immoral degradation of human rights and freedoms by human beings, is an unforgivable crime!

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